

HISTOLOGICAL STUDIES ON THE DOG'S SPLEEN

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the present research is to study the histological structure of the dog's spleen concerning the closed type of blood circulation. The spleens of 6 mixed breed dogs, one French Bulldog and one Yorkshire terrier, all with an unfavorable diagnosis and without pathological involvement of the organ were examined. The drugs used in the different protocols of euthanasia varied, and so as their effect on the constriction and relaxation of the venous sinuses located in the dog's spleen. A conventional histological examination was performed and the closed type of circulation, relaxation, and overflowing of the splenic sinuses with precipitates from erythrocyte masses were observed.

Key words: spleen, dog, histology, *sinus lienalis*, closed type of circulation.

Introduction

The detailed anatomical and histological structure of the spleen, and its blood vessels, are well-studied and described in the scientific literature (Bacha & Bacha, 2012; Konig & Leibich, 2020; Sapundjiev and Chervenkov, 2020; Vodenicharov et al., 2021). Banks (1993) divides the spleens of domestic animals into three main types – protective, reservoir, and mixed, according to the arrangement and amount of the capsular and trabecular smooth muscle fibers. The first type found in rabbits and humans contains fewer trabeculae and muscle fibers, but an abundance of lymphatic tissue (white pulp). More trabeculae and muscle fibers, but less white pulp is presented in the reservoir type of spleen owned by the horse, dog, and cat. The third type named mixed is found in ruminants and pigs. On the other hand, Singh (2018) classifies the spleens regarding their ability to change in shape and size, which is related to the number of trabeculae and muscle fibers. They divide it into sinusoidal and non-sinusoidal. The canine spleen is a sinusoidal type and can store a large amount of blood for rapid release in an emergency (Bacha & Bacha, 2012), as also the spleen of the camel (Zidan et al. 2000).

The blood circulation of the spleen is divided into two types, based on the end of the terminal capillaries. The first one, called closed type and found in dogs, humans, and some laboratory animals, owes capillaries that open into *sinus venulares (lienalis, venosus)*. In the open type of blood circulation observed in ruminants, equids, pigs, and cats the terminal capillaries continue into *vasa capillaria sinusoida*. The last disperse into the chordae of the red pulp from where the postcapillary venular drainage begins. Then, regardless of the type of blood circulation, the blood goes into *venae pulpae rubrae*, and then to *venae trabeculares*.

According to Kniseley 1936, the venous sinuses have a physiological sphincter at their efferent end before it passes into the veins of the red pulp. In dogs, during rest, the blood vessels in the spleen relax and get filled with blood, which is also observed when treated with some anaesthetics – ketamine and diazepam. This increases the size of the spleen (Wilson *et al.*, 2004; Singh, 2018). While running, under stress or treatment with catecholamines the blood rich in erythrocytes, lymphocytes, and plasma from the venous sinuses enters the general bloodstream (Singh 2018). Relaxation of the

physiological sphincter is also observed under anesthesia with acepromazine and propofol but with no change in the spleen's size (Wilson et al. 2004). The filling interval of the venous sinuses to *vena pulpae rubrae* has a cyclicity that varies from a few minutes to 10 hours according to Hermanson 2020.

The analysis of the literature data directed the authors to study the histological structure of the spleen in relation to its type of blood circulation under the effect of different anaesthetics, which results as a change in the spleen's size.

Materials and methods

Materials

For the purposes of the present study spleens from eight dogs were used – 6 mixed breed dogs (3 male and 3 females with average weight of 15 kg), one female French Bulldog, and one male Yorkshire terrier. All the above patients were diagnosed unfavourable, as their pathological condition was unrelated to the spleen. Seven of the dogs underwent planned euthanasia with the following anaesthetic protocols, described in Table 1. The last one died from natural death. No ethical approval was necessary for the use of the canine cadavers. At the end of the study the cadavers were incinerated.

Table 1: Anaesthetic protocols used.

Protocol	Anaesthetics	Number of animals
XA	Xylazine (1 – 2 mg/kg IM), Acepromazine (0.2 mg/kg IM)	3
XKP	Xylazine (1 – 2 mg/kg IM), Ketamine (10 mg/kg IM), Propofol (3 – 8 mg/kg IV)	2
KD	Ketamine (10 mg/kg IM), Diazepam (0.5 – 2 mg/kg IM)	2

Methods

Histological examination with hematoxylin-eosin staining

Samples from the dorsal, middle, and ventral parts of the spleen were collected in 10% formaldehyde. The so fixed samples were embedded in paraffin and section with 5–10 µm thickness were prepared. Subsequently, the samples were stained through the hematoxylin and eosin method (Georgiev 2014, Ruzhanova-Gospodinova 2021; Hristakiev 2022). The microscopic examination and photography were performed with a Levenhuk D740T light microscope with an integrated camera, and the morphometric studies were conducted through LevenhukLite image processing software. For the naming of the visualized structures were used the anatomical (Simoens *et al.* NAV, 2017; Constantinescu, 2018) and the histological (Seeger et al. NHV, 2017) nomenclature.

Results

The trabeculae (*trabeculae splenicae*) and the capsule were found rich in smooth muscle cells. In the trabeculae were visualized the arteries – *arteriae trabeculares* and the veins – *venae trabeculares*. The arteries of the white pulp – *arteriae pulpae albae* starting from the trabecular arteries were also detected. Around them was observed the splenic lymph node (*lymphonodus splenicus*) as a compact lymphoid tissue, where the name of the vessel is changed to an artery of the lymph node (*arteria lymphonoduli*) or central artery (*arteria centralis*). The last was established both on transverse and longitudinal sections peripherally and centrally in the lymph node (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Histological section of the dorsal end of the spleen of the dog under KD (Ketamine, diazepam) protocol H&E x4 – Trab. – Trabecula; a. trab. -arteria trabecularis; v. trab. – vena trabecularis; a. c. – arteria centralis; s. v. – filled sinus venularis, venosus, lienalis; lymph. spl. – lymphonodulus splenicus; a. pen. – arteriolae penicillares; elips – elipsoid

Outside of the borders of the white pulp (*pulpa lienis alba/pulpa alba*) the vessel is directed to the red pulp as *arteriae pulpa rubrae* and located eccentrically in the splenic lobe. The marginal zone – a transition between white and red pulp, together with the arteries of the red pulp was visualized in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Histological section of the middle part of the spleen of the dog under KD (Ketamine, diazepam) protocol H&E x10 – a. p. r. pulpa rubra; Trab. – Trabecula; a. trab. -arteria trabecularis; a. c. – arteria centralis; s. v. – full sinus venularis, venosus, lienalis; lymph. spl. – lymphonodulus splenicus; a. pen. arteriolae penicillares; aa. elips. – arteriolae elipsoideae, MZ – marginal zone

At the red pulp were seen the connective tissue formations called *chordae splenicae* (Fig. 3). The arteries of the red pulp were established, dividing into several brush-like arterioles (*arteriolae*

penicillares) and each of them was divided into two or three precapillary ellipsoidal arterioles (*arteriolae elipsoideae*) (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Histological section of the dorsal of the spleen of the dog under XKP (Xylazine, ketamine, propofol) protocol H&E x4 – p. r. – pulpa rubra; Trab. – Trabecula splenicae; ch. spl. – chordae splenicae; a. c. – arteria centralis; s. v. – empty sinus venularis (venosus, lienis); lymph. spl. – lymphonodulus splenicus; a. p. r. – arteria pulpae rubre; p. a. – pulpa alba; a. p. al. – arteria pulpae albae; elips – elipsoid.

The end of the final capillaries corresponds to the closed type of blood circulation in venous sinuses (*sinus venulares, lienis, venosus*) visible in Figures 1, 2, and 3. The venous sinuses were established flattened or filled with erythrocytes or erythrocyte formalin precipitates (clusters) with hemosiderin (Fig. 4 A; 4 B).

Figure 4: Histological sections of the ventral ends (A) middle part (B) of the spleen of the dog under KD (Ketamine, diazepam) H&E x4 – lymph. spl. – lymphonodulus splenicus; p.r. – pulpa rubra; elips. – elipsoid; trab. – trabecula; cap – capsula; a.c. – arteria centralis; Epf+h – erythrocyte formalin precipitates with hemosiderin.

The veins that collect the blood from the venous sinuses were not identified by the present study, but their continuation as a trabecular vein was (Fig. 1).

To evaluate the effect of different anaesthetics on the spleen the authors compared the white-to-red pulp ratio for each anesthetic protocol with the use of LevenhukLite image processing software. In the spleens from the animals on XA and XKA protocol, as the one that died from a natural cause, the ratio was 1:1 (Fig. 5 A; 5 B). A substantial change of this ratio was established in the spleen from the patient under KD anesthetic protocol, where the white to a red pulp was 1:5, due to the overflowing splenic sinuses in the red pulp (Fig. 5C). It was also observed that the strongest change in both ratio and color was at the ventral end of the spleen (Fig. 5C).

Figure 5: Histological sections of the ventral end of the spleen of the dog under XKP (Xylazine, ketamine, propofol) protocol (A), natural cause of dead (B) and under KD (Ketamine, diazepam) protocol (C). H&E x4 (A, C), H&E x 40 (B) – p.a. – pulpa alba; p.r. – pulpa rubra; a. trab – arteria trabecularis; v. trab – vena trabecularis; trab. – trabecula.

Discussion

The presence of numerous smooth muscle cells in the trabeculae and the relatively high number of trabeculae detected by the present study corresponds to the findings described by Bacha and Bacha, 2012 who classified the spleen of the dog as a reservoir type. The detailed histological structure of the spleen and its blood supply described by us confirms the data from the scientific literature (Seeger et al. (NHV), 2017; Sapundjiev & Chervenkov, 2021; Vodenicharov et al., 2021). The terminal capillaries end as a closed type of circulation, which is typical in the dog, man, Malayan bear, rat, and camel in which they open into venous sinuses (*sinus venulares, lienis, venosus*). The microcirculation and terminal vascular bed are thus described by Zidan et al. (2000), Press C. McL. & T. Landsverk (2006), Kalita et al. (2021), and Sapundjiev & Chervenkov (2021) and were illustrated by the present study.

In the splenic sinuses erythrocyte-formalin masses with hemosiderin, released from the hemolysis of the red blood cells were observed. This gives the rusty-brown color to the histological sections of the spleen and was described by Valli et al. (2016) in some pathological conditions – hemolytic and iron-deficiency anaemia in animals. In the present study, the spleens of the dogs were not pathomorphological changed, which makes these clusters a normal finding in the spleen under the action of the formaldehyde on the erythrocyte masses. The sphincter on the efferent end of the venous sinus was not visualized by us in histological sections, as it is not a morphologically distinguishable structure, but a physiological one according to Kniseley (1936) and described later by Hermanson (2020). Trabecular veins of different calibers reported by Seeger *et al.* (NHV), 2017, and Sapundjiev and Chervenkov (2021) were also identified by the present study. The lack of histological splenic change under XA and XKP protocols anaesthesia and the strong change found on the spleen of the dog under XD protocol is a histological confirmation of the performed macroscopic measurements of the spleen reported by Wilson (2004). This research detected microscopically that the ventral end of the spleen is of great change, which confirms the data on the variation, size, and shape of the same part of the spleen described by Hermanson (2020).

Conclusion

The splenic structure and the closed type of blood circulation in the dog were confirmed in histological sections. Comparing the histological changes of the spleen according to the different anaesthetic protocols and the ratio of white to red spleen pulp was used. It was concluded that there is no change in the normal splenic structure with a ratio of 1:1 detected on the spleens of the dogs under XA and XKP anaesthesia, but under XD protocol the ratio changed to 1:5. Understanding the histological structure of the spleen of the dog and its changes under the action of different drugs is of great use for veterinary surgery and internal diseases.

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